

D4.6 – Evolutive infrastructure inventory - Report Nr 2

Project Title	A network of excellence for distributed, trustworthy, efficient and scalable AI at the Edge
Project Acronym	dAIEDGE
Grant Agreement No	101120726
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2022-HUMAN-02-02
Start Date of Project	September 1 st , 2023
Duration of Project	36 Months

Name of the Deliverable	Evolutive infrastructure inventory - Report Nr 2
Number of the Deliverable	D4.6
Related WP Number and Name	WP4 - Next-gen NoE Framework and Infrastructure Federation
Related Task Number and Name	T4.1 Infrastructure inventory and testbeds federation
Deliverable Dissemination Level	PU - Public
Deliverable Due Date	M12 – August 2024 – New due date M13 – September 2024
Deliverable Submission Date	30.09.2024
Task Leader/Main Author	BTH
Contributing Partners	BTH
Reviewer(s)	USAL, BCA

Keywords

Inventory, edge AI objects, sustainability, benchmarking, interoperability, incentivization

Revisions

Version	Submission date	Comments	Author
v0.1	2024-09-24	Version for internal review	BTH
v0.2	2024-09-27	Version for coordinator review	BTH, USAL, BCA
v1.0	2024-09-30	Final version	BTH, USAL, BCA, DFKI

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Acronyms and definitions

Acronym	Meaning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
GA	General Assembly
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
vLab	Virtual Lab
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This second version of the evolutive infrastructure inventory (Report Nr 2, Deliverable D4.6) provides four major inputs to a sustained and secure design of it within the dAIEDGE Virtual Lab (vLab). These major inputs are:

1. It lists additional edge AI hardware and software resources available for sharing and usage in the vLab, i.e. it improves the quality of the information in the inventory.
2. It outlines the expected real-world architecture of inventory in the vLab using the use case of benchmarking.
3. It discusses and suggests techniques for a sustainable evolutionary infrastructure inventory. The suggested concept and techniques are:
 - a. A more detailed requirement catalog on the inventory and its data structure
 - b. Frond-end and back-end functions for the continuous improvement of the Inventory and its integration with vLab
 - c. The initial usage of the central vLab server as the main integration and orchestration entity for the vLab.
 - d. ODRL for the Interoperability and trustful use of the vLab.
 - e. Techniques to incentivize resource contributions to the vLab.
4. A timeline until the end of the runtime of task T4.1, which details the activities in task T4.1 and the interworking with the other tasks.

Finally, it briefly discussed future technical and research work in task T4.1 and why it should focus on a secure and distributed incentivization concept for the self-management of the evolutive infrastructure inventory.

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1. Introduction

The vLab is a unique feature of the dAIEDGE project and is one of the tools to facilitate and accelerate research of edge AI. The uniqueness is expected to come of the variety of edge AI resources available in the dAIEDGE consortium, and beyond, and to engage and integrate distributed users and AI objects into experimentation and data-driven research on edge AI.

A major competent of the vLab is the evolutive edge AI object infrastructure inventory, cf. [D4.1]. An inventory typically consists of information about objects in a system (e.g. available AI objects) and a data structure, e.g. a data bases, where users can search for the objects, retrieve information about the object, and update the state of the object (e.g. whether an object is available). An inventory needs to be managed, i.e. its content should reflect the state of the system, i.e. the vLab and including new objects (or the removal of old objects). Typically, the management of an inventory should be automatic, e.g. by an active search process or a self-management mechanism.

The previous deliverable D4.1 (M6 report; Report Nr. 1) was able to catalog a very large number of edge AI objects available in the dAIEDGE project. The quality and comprehensiveness of the catalog was of a high level. In addition, D4.1 outlined initial techniques to obtain an even higher comprehensiveness as a high longevity and sustainability of the catalog,

This deliverable D4.6 (M12 report; Report Nr 2) will improve and refine the work achieved by D4.1 by using a well-adapted and structured process. It will identify new resources available in the consortium and verify whether all identified resources are still available.

However, its focus is on the activities and techniques required for the sustainability and longevity of the inventory. Hence, D4.6 will discuss various requirements and techniques for sustainability, like data base requirements, architectural choices in context of the vLab server, frontend design, etc. but also incentivization mechanism for enabling a trustful use of the vLab and a self-management of the inventory, that will be implemented in the blockchain layer of the middleware.

This document is organized as follows. Section 2. Updated Data Acquisition and Evolution Strategy explains the updated data acquisition and evolution strategy for the inventory. Section 3.

New Resources in the Evolutive Infrastructure Inventory details the new resources in the inventory and the availability of the resources. Section 4. Benchmarking Resources discussed the interaction of the inventory with the vLab using the first use case of the inventory on benchmarking. Section 5. Sustainability of the Inventory focuses on the sustainability and longevity activities and provide a time for them until the of the runtime of the task, i.e. the end of the dAIEDGE project. Finally, Section 6. Conclusion summarizes the presented information and give an outlook in potential research work in the task.

2. Updated Data Acquisition and Evolution Strategy

Deliverable D4.1 outlined a second phase of the data acquisition and evolution strategy of the infrastructure inventory of edge AI resources in dAIEDGE, cf. Section 3.3.3 in [D4.1]. The strategy

aims at a continuous update and refinement of an inventory repository and its sustainability. It focuses on the content of the inventory and its comprehensiveness, which are typically the major features of an inventory. For a time horizon, the strategy aims at two kind of activities, short-term ones, i.e. mainly evolving the quality of the current inventory information, and longer-term activities, i.e. considering the inventory’s sustainability or longevity, e.g. being able to be updated, usage in production of experiments, and interoperability. The strategy in [D4.1] is structured into eight steps and depicted in the column “Original Steps and Activities” of Table 1. The column also outlines the expected time horizon and ways of completing the activity.

Original Steps and Activities			Updated Steps and Activities					
Step	Activity	Time horizon / way of completion	Activity	Time horizon / way of completion				
1	Presentation of the first result to the consortium	Short-term / Completed at dAIEDGE general assembly (GA) at M06	–	–				
2	Improved gap analysis based on available information and improved activity planning.	Short-term / Completed at M06; coordinated with WP4 leader	–	–				
3	First (targeted) round of information collection from partners.	Short-term	Single targeted round of information collection from partners; documented in Section 3.1.	Completed at dAIEDGE GA at M12				
4	Verification of database (data) structure for the inventory	Longer-term	To be accomplished by Section 3.2 in this deliverable	<p>Section Table 4 outlines the semantics of the interaction points of the inventory with the benchmarking. Finally, it should be noted that benchmarking is a first use case, and more uses will guide and drive the vLab design. Hence, T4.1 expects an iterative improvement and generalization of the APIs offered by the inventory for the AI engineering process in the vLab.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interaction Point</th> <th>Semantic</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>“selecting from the inventory”</td> <td>An authenticated and</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interaction Point	Semantic	“selecting from the inventory”	An authenticated and
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<p><i>Table 4: List of Interaction points for Benchmarking and their Semantic</i></p>					
<p>5. Sustainability of the Inventory)</p>					
5	Second (targeted) round of information collection from partners.	Short-term	Superseded by the results of the revised step 3.	Section 3. New Resources in the Evolutive Infrastructure Inventory)	

6	Defining a long-term sustainability plan for the inventory (Continuously updated).	Longer-term	Define a timeline until the end of the task, i.e. M12,	<p>Section Table 4 outlines the semantics of the interaction points of the inventory with the benchmarking. Finally, it should be noted that benchmarking is a first use case, and more uses will guide and drive the vLab design. Hence, T4.1 expects an iterative improvement and generalization of the APIs offered by the inventory for the AI engineering process in the vLab.</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="1023 750 1426 2065"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="1023 750 1201 846">Interaction Point</th> <th data-bbox="1201 750 1426 846">Semantic</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="1023 846 1201 1449">“selecting from the inventory”</td> <td data-bbox="1201 846 1426 1449">An authenticated and authorized user can browse (incl. searching) through the inventory. The inventory provides a list of resources (incl. technical features and availability).</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1023 1449 1201 1897">“locking the resources in the inventory”</td> <td data-bbox="1201 1449 1426 1897">The vLab server requests the inventory to lock the resources (if needed) for exclusive use while conducting the benchmarking.</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="1023 1897 1201 2065">“vLab server releases the</td> <td data-bbox="1201 1897 1426 2065">The vLab server informs the inventory that the</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interaction Point	Semantic	“selecting from the inventory”	An authenticated and authorized user can browse (incl. searching) through the inventory. The inventory provides a list of resources (incl. technical features and availability).	“locking the resources in the inventory”	The vLab server requests the inventory to lock the resources (if needed) for exclusive use while conducting the benchmarking.	“vLab server releases the	The vLab server informs the inventory that the
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7	Update of database structure for inventory.	Longer-term	Definition of requirements for database structure	<p>Section Table 4 outlines the semantics of the interaction points of the inventory with the benchmarking. Finally, it should be noted that benchmarking is a first use case, and more uses will guide and drive the vLab design. Hence, T4.1 expects an iterative improvement and generalization of the APIs offered by the inventory for the AI engineering process in the vLab.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interaction Point</th> <th>Semantic</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>“selecting from the inventory”</td> <td>An authenticated and authorized user can browse (incl. searching) through the inventory. The inventory provides a list of resources (incl. technical features and availability).</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Interaction Point	Semantic	“selecting from the inventory”	An authenticated and authorized user can browse (incl. searching) through the inventory. The inventory provides a list of resources (incl. technical features and availability).
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8	Controlling the inventory quality (targeting all partners).	Longer-term	Verification of database structure for inventory using an email survey	<p>Completed by 2024-09-18; Section Table 4 outlines the semantics Of the interaction points of the inventory with the benchmarking. Finally, it should be noted that benchmarking is a first use case, and more uses will guide and drive the vLab design. Hence, T4.1 expects an iterative improvement and generalization of the APIs offered by the inventory for the AI engineering process in the vLab.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Interaction Point</th> <th>Semantic</th> </tr> </thead> </table>	Interaction Point	Semantic		
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Table 1: Steps of the Data Acquisition and Evolution Strategy of the Infrastructure Inventory

Updated Strategy

It turned out during the discussion at dAIEDGE general assembly in Sofia at Month 6 (M06) that the content of inventory as of [D4.1] was already quite comprehensive and beyond expectation (according to the WP4 leader). The inventory content enables a thorough planning and design of the vLab in the subsequent tasks in WP4, i.e. task 4.2 (“Virtual research lab design”), task 4.3 (“Scheduling optimization and ML model deployment”) and task 4.4 (“Virtual research lab development”).

Hence, the discussions at the general assembly and within WP4 have led to an updated data acquisition and evolution strategy, cf. “Updated Steps and Activities” in Table 1. The refined activities focus on steps 4, 6, and 7, i.e. the sustainability and longevity of the inventory (rather than on improving the quality of the content only). However, some of the tasks in WP4 that need to interact with inventory on its longevity, i.e. which provide input to D4.6, are just in the starting phase, e.g. T4.4. Finally, sustainability work in T4.1 is planned to continue beyond the deadline of D4.6. Hence, D4.6 describes also the future work to be done in T4.1. Sections 4, 5, and 6 in this document are addressing the future activities of task T4.1.

3. New Resources in the Evolutive Infrastructure Inventory

Deliverable D4.1 collected a significant number (> 35) of edge and cloud-based AI core services and objects available in dAIEDGE. Figure 1: Types of Edge AI Service and Objects Available in the Inventory of D4.1 reveals that more than half of the objects are edge models, software, and data, while only a few of the relevant resources are available in the Cloud. Furthermore, many edge AI hardware objects are readily available for usage.

Types of Edge AI Core Services and Objects Contributed to the vLabs and Available in the D4.1 Inventory Version .

Figure 1: Types of Edge AI Service and Objects Available in the Inventory of D4.1.

3.1 Enhancements in the M12 Version (D4.6)

Before and after the M12 general assembly, T4.1 conducted a new and targeted round of surveys and responses from partners. This time the process approached consortium partners, who were unable to answer comprehensively the survey of [D4.1]. Table 2 outlines the newly added resources from this iteration. As expected, the inventory was already complete and only a few additional resources to were added the inventory, cf. **Error! Reference source not found.** However, the

addition of these important resources also shows the necessity of a continuous improvement of the content of the inventory.

New Resource	Partner
Edge AI Models	Vicomtech
Two speech enhancement AI models: “Tinydenoiser”-based on recurrent layers (https://github.com/GreenWavesTechnologies/tiny_denoiser) “MP-Senet” – based on complex layers (https://github.com/yxlu-0102/MP-SENet/blob/main/train.py)	Thales SIX
New edge AI hardware: Raspberry Pi platform replaced by Jetson Nano Orin.	FORTH

Table 2: New resources in M12 by D4.6

In the second iteration of the survey two additional responses from the partners “Vicomech” and “Thales SIX” were provided. They are contributing software resources such as edge AI models and frameworks.

Furthermore, these partners are using Lightweight Directory Access Protocol (LDAP) and local solutions for managing user authentication and authorization. They are making use of controlled and monitored code repositories such as GIT for community building.

Availability of the Current Information in the Inventory

Since vLab is not yet finalized, it is currently not advised to implement an advanced inventory, i.e. complex database system. Hence, the information on resources in the inventory is currently available as an Excel file at [dAledegInv].

3.2 Verification of Resources

An important feature of an inventory is the active verification of whether the objects in the inventory are still available and that the information about the features of the objects is correct. When vLab and middleware could be deployed in partner's nodes each partner authenticated in the blockchain could verify the status of their inventory and change it if necessary.

While the inventory eventually aims at an automatic process for verification, confirmation of the inventory at the design stage can only be done manually. Hence, T4.1 conducted an email survey after the Heraklion GA and asked the consortium to actively object if the resources in the Excel file of the inventory are not available or not up to date. This survey reveals no significant change, even new resources were added (see FORTH in Table 2), but all the already communicated resources are still available.

4. Benchmarking Resources

The approach of T4.1 on evolving the inventory is based on dAIEDGE concept of driving the development and research of distributed edge AI by use case, and in turn, handling the complexity of the scenario. The use cases will define the requirements and implementations. Subsequently, the

findings of the implementation will be generalized and, perhaps, refine the requirements. All in all, this is a development and research concept that is inspired by modern agile software development, cf. [Abra02].

The first use case of the vLab is being a distributed platform for benchmarking AI models running on remote boards (see D4.2 - Distributed Network Design) The preliminary scenario and architecture of the vLab for benchmarking is depicted in Figure 2, which was provided with courtesy by T4.4. It shows the vLab, its users, the remote-host, and the remote server. The web-interface and remote server can be used to orchestrate the benchmarking in the initial step of the benchmarking process, while the remote-hosts produce the benchmarking results locally.

Figure 2: The early vLab Architecture for Remote and Distributed Benchmarking, cf. [WP4Hera]

The generally available benchmarking resources in the inventory for this use case are listed in **Error! Reference source not found.** This list of benchmarking resources, however, is expected to grow in feature. dodge has a particular task, T7.1, that focuses on benchmarks for micro, deep, and meta-Edge AI, cf. [dAIEDGE]

We expect that in the future, a user can scan through the inventory, and find suited models, remote-hosts, and benchmarking resources. The backend system of the vLab together with inventory locks required resources for exclusive and immediate use, supports the benchmarking using automation and orchestration techniques, and finally returns the resources for future re-use. The data structure of the inventory might interconnect the catalog of the resources with their usage status.

Available Benchmarking Resources	The partner who is offering the Resource
AI Witchlabs Benchmark	INSAIT
GATE (benchmarking suite for broader ML models, adaptably for edge cases)	University of Edinburgh
Benchmarking service on target edge devices	HES-SO

Table 3: Benchmarking resources

Interaction of the Inventory with Benchmarking

The initial version benchmarking step for a typical use case is depicted in Figure 3. The four steps focus on the selection of resources and conducting benchmarking. Step 1 selects the model, the remote hosts, and the benchmark. Step 2 is the deployment of target-specific scripts (AI-Support, AI-Build, AI-Deploy, AI-Manager) on the remote host, while step 3 is building target-specific binary on the remote host and executing the benchmarking. Finally, step 4 collects the benchmarking results and sends them back to the user via the vLab server.

1. A *Remote-user#* initiates a benchmarking request via a web interface, selecting the **model** to be benchmarked, the **target** *Remote-node#*, and the Machine Learning Runtime (**MLR**) to be used..
2. The Vlab server processes the *Remote-user#* request by executing target-specific scripts (AI-Support, AI-Build, AI-Deploy, AI-Manager) through the Gitlab runner on the remote host managing the *Remote-node#*. A Docker container containing the necessary target-specific tools is then deployed and run on the remote host.
3. The remote host runs the target-specific scripts (**AI-Support, AI-Build, AI-Deploy, AI-Manager**) using the tools within the Docker container. This process generates a target-specific binary, which is then deployed onto the target *Remote-node#*.
4. The remote host collects the benchmarking metrics from the target *Remote-node#* and sends them back to the Vlab server, allowing the *Remote-user#* to view them via the web interface.

Figure 3: Remote Benchmarking Process,

Figure 4 shows some of the opportunities for interaction of the remote benchmarking process with the inventory. These interaction points are marked by font in bold and underlined. The points will become APIs and technical interfaces for the inventory when released.

1. A *Remote-user#* initiates a benchmarking request via a web interface, selecting **from the inventory** the **model** to be benchmarked, the **target** *Remote-node#*, and the Machine Learning Runtime (**MLR**) to be used..
2. The Vlab server processes the *Remote-user#* request by checking the **locking the resources in the inventory** executing target-specific scripts (AI-Support, AI-Build, AI-Deploy, AI-Manager) through the Gitlab runner on the remote host managing the *Remote-node#*. A Docker container containing the necessary target-specific tools is then deployed and run on the remote host.
3. The remote host runs the target-specific scripts (**AI-Support, AI-Build, AI-Deploy, AI-Manager**) using the tools within the Docker container. This process generates a target-specific binary, which is then deployed onto the target *Remote-node#*.
4. The remote host collects the benchmarking metrics from the target *Remote-node#* and sends them back to the Vlab server, allowing the *Remote-user#* to view them via the web interface. Finally, the **Vlab server releases the resources and updates the inventory.**

Figure 4: Interaction of the Remote Benchmarking Process with the Inventor, based on Figure 3.

Table 4 outlines the semantics of the interaction points of the inventory with the benchmarking. Finally, it should be noted that benchmarking is a first use case, and more uses will guide and drive the vLab design. Hence, T4.1 expects an iterative improvement and generalization of the APIs offered by the inventory for the AI engineering process in the vLab.

Interaction Point	Semantic
“selecting from the inventory”	An authenticated and authorized user can browse (incl. searching) through the inventory. The inventory provides a list of resources (incl. technical features and availability).
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Table 4: List of Interaction points for Benchmarking and their Semantic

5. Sustainability of the Inventory

The sustainability and longevity of the Inventory is a design challenge that defines how the inventory is maintained over a longer period, potentially beyond the end of the dAIEDGE project. The challenge addresses the useability of the inventory in the context of the use of vLab and this capability to remain useful even after the project.

5.1 Requirements on the Inventory and its Data Structure

The resources contributed by the involved partners are subject to modification at any given time. This includes recalling the resource availability or adding new resources to the inventory and updating the access controls. In detail, the inventory should provide an up-to-date understanding of the available resources for dAIEDGE, including their current use, the reflection of changes in the inventory, etc. Hence, the infrastructure inventory needs to accommodate the dynamically evolving user contributions by allowing continuous updates to the resources within the vLab.

Furthermore, interoperability has a decisive role in the long-term suitability of the inventory, since it allows cooperation with partners and resources outside the dAIEDGE consortium. It should be easy to add or transfer resources from the outside, e.g. similar platforms, into the vLab. This is expected to contribute to a network effort and increase the value of the vLab beyond the consortium.

Finally, there is a need for the inventory to support and protect the intellectual property rights (IPRs) management of the contributed resources. Here, the proven license management form BonApps [D3.4] serves as a foundation for describing and even negotiating the usage rights and policies for the resources. The alignment of the license file contents and syntax with open standards, e.g. ODRL, can contribute to the wide adoption of the inventory. Licenses might also help to include other data source providers such as the European AU-on-Demand project.

Next, we will provide an overview of the substantivity plan for maintaining the evolving infrastructure inventory that consists of (1) Continuous improvement of the inventory & integration with vLab (2) Interoperability of the inventory resources (3) Incentivization of the resource contribution, and (4) a timeline for activities for sustainability for remaining runtime of the task T4.1, i.e. until M36 of the project.

5.2 Continuous Improvement of the Inventory & Integration with vLab

In order to maintain the inventory under dynamically evolving user contributions, there is a requirement for the vLab design to have appropriate functionalities and design correct APIs and data structures in place. This deliverable identifies such functionalities to be added to the vLab front-end as well as to the backend structure of the vLab and the inventory database. These functions are outlined in **Error! Reference source not found.** Special focus within the functionalities is laid on license management, which has been shown to be pivotal for trustful distributed AI engineering, cf. [BonsApps 3.4]. Hence, Table 5 outlined in addition to the typical and fundament inventory management functions, ones for license management and for building trust in the vLab. The column priority in Table 5 indicated which function needs in the opinion of T4.1 be implemented first.

Implementation Scope	Description	Priority
<i>Front-end Functions</i>	Add, delete, and update resources (incl. update of the inventory data structure)	Fundamental
	Browse, and select resources,	Fundamental
	User control for licenses: editor for License content:	Trust-building
	User control for licenses: engagement and joint approval	Trust-building
<i>Back-end or Middleware Functions</i>	Interaction with user management (authentication and authorization)	Fundamental
	Reservation, logging, and freeing of resources (incl. coordination with orchestration of resources)	Fundamental
	Licenses: verification, generation, and enforcement (incl. coordination with orchestration of resources)	Trust-building
	Licenses: Distributed Storage and updating of licenses content	Trust-building

Table 5: Required Functions for the Inventory of Resources for the vLab

Inventory Database Structure

Currently, the inventory is organized as an Excel file as described in D4.1. This kind of data structure is apparently sufficient for short-term interactions, e.g. with the consortium collecting information and the vLab designers, see e.g. Task T4.4. Such a file has some advantages such that it can be quickly updated, and it is easy and readily accessible without the need for programming efforts.

However, it is expected that this data structure is not scalability to a larger number of users. Furthermore, it lacks the support for typical user management, e.g. for authentication and authorization at scale, nor does it have direct remote access. Finally, a user or a system can't do complex queries or updates on the inventory. Hence, a more complex data structure in the form of a database is indicated. This database will be designed in coordination with vLab requirements and vLab design, see tasks T4.2 and T4.4. The timeline for the data design is currently under discussion with other tasks.

5.3 Integration with vLab Architecture

The inventory database is integrated into the vLab website and under its frontend and backend parts. The placement is based on the original vLab architecture shown in Figure 2. Figure 5 depicts the placement of the inventory frontend and backend in vLab. These parts are basically located at the vLab webserver which is a centralized entity. However, if vLab required a more decentralized implementation, i.e. it should not be implemented on a single webserver but using peer-to-peer communication and Blockchains. This fully distributed architecture can be obtained by using methods and technologies outlined in [Tuts08] and [Tkac23]. However, a fully distributed solution for an inventory might require a significant development effort. The efforts should be considered in the context of the benefit of a distributed inventory repository.

Centralized Integration at the vLab Server

Whenever a user needs to perform an experiment using vLab resources, the front-end web interface guides the user in browsing through the resource catalog and requesting access to a particular resource, the common functions include *search & select*. Since vLab is equipped with multiple development and deployment pipelines, the users can order compute transactions directly from the vLab website & the backend will initiate nodes for processing the computation.

The contributing partners (or the owners of the resources) will be given access to edit (add, release) and update the vLab catalog using the front-end interface, the changes will be then directly reflected in the inventory database. By integrating the inventory database into the core functional requirements of the vLab, deliverable D4.6 foresees a sustainability plan for maintaining resources in a dynamic database.

The anticipated location of the inventory in the architecture of the vLab is depicted in Figure 5. The front-end of the inventory will be a webpage where users can select resources for experimentation as well as add and delete resources.

Figure 5: Inventory Architecture in Context of the vLab

Webpage Design and Mock-up Page

A mockup of the frontend webpage is shown Figure 6. The general objective of the webpage and frontend design are a) to provide the user of the inventory with GUI that is easy to use, b) which supports keeping the data up to date (incl. control of the updates by the user and trace), and c) which enables if possible automated self-management of the inventory.

As suggested above, the inventory should be placed initially placed at the vLab server which operates a front-end webserver. The users will interact with the inventory through these pages. The design of the pages is outlined next.

Objective 1: The vLab users need a mechanism that allows them to dynamically add resources to the inventory list.

It is assumed that a user, who is authenticated and authorized, can add resources to the inventory list using the front-end interface depicted in Figure 6a: Webpage for Adding edge Ai Resources to the Inventory. The first mock-up design shows a resource register page that contains the following fields that an authorized user can fill in (cf. also the username in the upper right corner): (1) "Unique Resource Name"- name the resource with a unique name made of combining userID, Resource name, and resource classification. (2) "Resource Type" - software or hardware (3) "Resource Location" - the physical location where the resource resides, in the case of software resource the location will be a link to the storage location (4) "Resource Usage Policies" - Link to the website or a document that describes the usage policies of the asset. At the bottom, there are terms and privacy conditions for registering resources in the dAIEDGE inventory. Then the "Register" button, upon clicking the button, the resource will be added to the inventory. Finally, there is an option to re-redirect users if they already have registered resources and want to make changes to them.

Objective 2: If the resource is already registered, the vLab users might want to update the resource details or permanently delete the resource from the inventory list.

The "Inventory Update" page is designed to fulfill the requirements of the vLab users in making updates to the resources or to remove the resources from the list, as shown in **Error! Reference**

source not found.. Under "Choose a resource" the user selects a resource out of the drop-down menu with a list of user contributions. Then the respective resource details such as "Resource Type", "Resource Location", and "Resource Usage policies" will be fetched and shown on the screen. The users can then make necessary changes to the resource list or check the existing details and then choose between the "update" or delete" options. Finally, the webpage shows a link that will redirect the users to register a resource page.

Forward Objective 3 – incentivization

The contributors of the vLab expect incentives regarding the use of their resources. Here, the incentives can be either decided by the vLab platform or the resource owners can directly specify the cost while registering into inventory.

The current version of the vLab does not include an incentivization mechanism due to the lack of interest in the contributing partners, and opinions gathered during D 4.1. However, incentivization is considered a part of vLab's long-term sustainability plan. Thus, section 5.5 points out the future directions for developing an incentivization model for vLab that rewards both software and hardware contributions. Therefore, incentivization is considered as a forward objective and planned to address while scaling the vLab platform.

dAIEdge Inventory Register U1: User_001
Logged In at: date and time

Please fill in this form to register a resource to the inventory.

Unique Resource Name
UserId+ResourceName & Type

Resource Type
Software or Hardware

Resource Location
Enter the location where the physical resource resides

Resource Usage Policies
Provide license agreements for utilizing the resources

By registering a resource you agree to our [Terms & Privacy](#).

Register

Already have a resource registered? [Edit](#).

Figure 6a: Webpage for Adding edge Ai Resources to the Inventory

Figure 7b: Webpage for Updating or Deleting an Object in the Inventory

5.4 Interoperability

Interoperability addresses the challenges involved in sharing the resources outside the consortium, to a larger audience, or to another consortium group. The use of standard human and machine-readable data structures for defining the licenses can contribute to the interoperability of the resources across similar platforms. By aligning the license file syntax and structure with standard rights expression languages such as ODRL, cf. [ODRL], the resource licenses can be processed outside the platform. The deliverable D4.6 plans to push the inventory list along with their license agreements into open-source repositories, thus the outside world can get an overview of the available resources and the scope for sharing the resources across other platforms.

5.5 Future Incentivization of Resource Contribution

The initial survey gathered the opinion of the contributing partners on the incentivization benefits for their respective resource contributions in the vLab or (for other shared computing pool services). The survey results suggest that most of the users either *don't expect any incentive* or *they are still figuring out the possibility*. However, ensuring an appropriate reward system to encourage the major contributors is necessary to maintain the stakeholder's interest in keep using the platform on a long-term basis. Hence, the sustainability plan aims to develop a flexible and secure incentivization model for maintaining vLab and the inventory. The incentivization should motivate trustful and continuous resource contribution, even from users beyond the consortium. This enables a kind of self-management of the inventory.

The existing literature proposed methods for monetizing the software [Kari22] and hardware [Amit19] contributions in data marketplaces, and federated learning scenarios. Nevertheless, the requirements and the use cases of the vLab can heavily influence the incentivization system. The scope for replying on distributed ledger technologies for similar purposes has been investigated [Meng20, Mark22, Rong22] to improve trust and transparency.

5.6 Timeline

The suggested timeline for defining and implementing a sustainable and evolutive inventory for the remainder of the dAIEDGE project of the runtime of task T4.1 is given in Table 6. The timeline aims on short-term to obtain a viable and working inventory and, on long-term, at improving the sustainability of the inventory by using incentivization of resource contributions for trust-building and as a technique to achieve continuous evolution of content within the data base over time.

Step	Activity	Executing Task in WP4	Date of Finalization
1	Decision of inventory data base type and capabilities of the vLab server, e.g. in context of orchestration and degree of decentralization	T4.1, T4.2	M15
2	Decision of the data structures in the inventory data base	T4.1	M16
3	Specification of the semantic and syntax of the interfaces and APIs for Fundamental Functions	T4.1, T4.2	M18
4	Specification of the Requirements for Trust-building using Incentivization	T4.1	M18
5	Specification of the semantic and syntax of the interfaces and APIs for trust-building functions for the inventory	T4.1	M21
6	Implementation of the fundamental inventory functions	T4.4	M24
7	Test and verification of fundamental inventory functions	T4.4	M23
8	Implementation of the trust-building and orchestration functions for the inventory	T4.4, T4.3	M27
9	Test and verification of trust-building functions	T4.4	M30

Table 6: Timeline for Task T4.1

6. Conclusion

This deliverable provides three major inputs to the sustained and secure design and implementation of the evolutive infrastructure inventory for dAIEDGE's vLab using a well-adapted methodology based on the significant progress achieved T4.1, WP4, and the dAIEDGE project at large. These major inputs are:

5. It lists new resources being available for sharing and usage by the vLab, i.e. it improves the quality of information in the inventory.
6. It outlines the expected and real-world architecture of vLab and the inventory using the use case of benchmarking, which is expect a major technique in dAIEDGE to improve the knowledge in edge AI.

7. It discusses and suggests techniques and concepts for a sustainable evolutionary infrastructure inventory for the vLab, and, in turn, it enables the longevity and the interoperability of the vLab. The suggested concept and techniques are:
 - a. Detailing the requirements on the inventory and its data structure
 - b. Frond-end and back-end functions for the Continuous Improvement of the Inventory and its integration with vLab
 - c. Initially, using the central vLab server as the main integration and orchestration entity.
 - d. Interoperability by ODRL for the trustful use of the vLab.
 - e. Techniques to incentivize resource contributions to the vLab.

8. A timeline until the end of the runtime of task T4.1 is suggested. The timeline details the activities in task T4.1 and its interworking with the other relevant tasks in WP4.

Future technical work in task T4.1, incl. research contribution, will mainly focus on the secure and distributed incentivization of AI edge resources contributed to the evolutive infrastructure inventory.

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